

A STUDY OF AWARENESS ABOUT ONLINE INFORMATION RESOURCES OF STUDENT TEACHERS

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Abstract

This paper is the experimental study conducted to find out the awareness level of student teachers before and after the conduction of online information resources training session. Sample selected for the study was 100 student teachers studying in the education colleges of Mumbai. Out of it 84 respondents were present for the session and responded to the experimental study very well. A questionnaire was distributed to students before and after the training session. A comparative analysis was done for the awareness level of students about online information resources before and after the training session. Finding show that their level of awareness was very much higher after the session as compared to before the session.

KEYWORDS: *Online Information Resources, Student Teachers, E-Books, E-Journals.*

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INTRODUCTION:

In today's world information is available on one click through internet with mobile, laptop, tab and computer devices. This information is available through various websites in the form of word, pdf, excel, and webpages. This information stands very useful for students studying in the colleges and schools. Bu whether students are aware about it? This study is about the student teachers studying in teacher education college. They need to have the knowledge of online information resources useful for their studies such as SSC and CBSE board e-books, electronic thesis and dissertation, open access books and journals available on the internet. These resources are available through E-Balbharati, E-Pathshala, Shodhganga, Shodhgangotri, ERIC, NLIST, NDLI, DOAJ and DOAB website. A training session was conducted for students for making them aware and also how to find out the information in

these resources. Following are the online information source websites taught to students during the training session.

- **E-Balbharati:**

It is official website of Secondary School Maharashtra State Board, which gives access to e-books of 1st to 12th standard. URL : <http://cart.ebalbharati.in/BalBooks/ebook.aspx>

- **E-Pathshala:**

It is the official website of Central Board of School Education, New Delhi. It gives access to e-books from standard 1 to standard 12. URL: - <https://epathshala.nic.in/>, <https://ncert.nic.in/>

- **ERIC**

Education Resource Information Centre (ERIC) is sponsored by Institute of Education Sciences (IES) of the U. S. Department of Education. It contains more than 1.5 million records and links to hundreds of thousands of full-text documents dating back to 1966. Includes Journal Articles, Books, Conference Papers, Curriculum Guides, Policy Papers, etc. URL: <https://eric.ed.gov/>

- **Shodhganga:**

It is the Digital Repository of Indian Electronic Theses and Dissertations set-up by the INFLIBNET centre. Open access facility is provided to users. Around 2,77,475 thesis from 475 universities are uploaded on the site. URL : <http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/>

- **Shodhgangotri**

It is the Repository of Indian Research in Progress. Research Proposal / Synopsis submitted to universities by the research scholar are uploaded on this site. Open access facility is available to users. URL : <http://shodhgangotri.inflibnet.ac.in/>

- **NLIST**

NLIST is National Library and Information Services Infrastructure for Scholarly Content. It is jointly run by UGC-INFONET, INFLIBNET Centre and the INDEST-AICTE Consortium, IIT Delhi. It has more than 135000 E-books and more than 6000 E-journals. URL: - <http://nlist.inflibnet.ac.in>

- **NDLI**

NDLI is National Digital Library of India. It is developed by the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD). It is useful for students (of all levels), teachers, researchers, librarians, library users, professionals, differently abled users, entrance/competitive examiners and all other lifelong learners. It has more than 5,02,53,589 e-books, e-journals, videos, presentations, etc. URL: <https://ndl.iitkgp.ac.in/>

- **DOAJ:**

It is the Directory of Open Access Journals. Access to high quality open access peer-reviewed more than 15, 073 journals I sprovided. URL: <https://doaj.org/>

- **DOAB:**

It is the Directory of Open Access Books. It provides access to More than 29,699 free e-books. URL : <https://www.doabooks.org/>

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

Alagu and Thanuskodi in 2018 conducted a case study to investigate the use and user perception of electronic Information resources of Alagappa College of Arts and science. The aim was to check students' awareness of e-resources and satisfaction level and problems faced by users while using e-resources. The descriptive survey method was used for the study. 120 questionnaires were distributed in the college out of which 80 respondents submitted their responses. Data were analyzed using a simple percentage technique. For the analysis of data, the simple percentage technique was used. Findings show that the majority of respondents have low knowledge of e-resources, insufficient infrastructure, and insufficient training are major concerns for accessing electronic resources. Whereas the majority of the respondents are using search engines than subscribed databases for accessing electronic resources.

Adetunla, G. O. (2016) conducted a study to understand the University libraries are investing huge amount of money to provide useful and accessible information services to users in electronic format to enhance learning and research activities. In order to justify the investment made on electronic information resources, this study examined awareness, perceived ease and use of EIR by undergraduate students of private university in Oyo state, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey design with a study population of 2,171 undergraduate students. Multi-stage sampling technique was used for selecting the sampled respondents for the study. Questionnaire was used for data collection which was analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson product moment correlation. The findings revealed that EIR was perceived to be complex, non-flexible and not easy to use. More so, the use of EIR does not meet the information needs of the students. The major challenge faced by student when using EIR was found to be frequent power cut with 75% respondent rate. The finding also revealed a positive relationship between perceived ease and use of EIR at (($p=0.00$; $p<0.05$).

Adeleke & Nwalo (2017). Availability, awareness and use of electronic resources provide access to authoritative, reliable, accurate and timely access to information. The use of electronic information resources (EIRs) can enable innovation in teaching and increase timeliness in research of postgraduate students which will eventual result into encouragement of the expected research-led

enquiry in this digital age. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Samples of 300 of postgraduate students within seven out of 13 Faculties were randomly selected. Data were collected using questionnaire designed to elicit response from respondents and data were analyzed using descriptive statistics methods percentages, mean, and standard deviation. Results indicated that internet was ranked most available and used in the university. Low level of usage of electronic resources, in particular, full texts data bases is linked to a number of constraints: Interrupted power supply was ranked highest among other factors as speed and capacity of computers, retrieval of records with high recall and low precision, retrieving records relevant to information need, lack of knowledge of search techniques to retrieve information effectively, non possession of requisite IT skills and problems accessing the internet. The study recommended that usage of electronic resources be made compulsory, intensifying awareness campaigns concerning the availability, training on use of electronic resources and the problem of power outage be addressed.

Sivathaasan, Murugathas and Chandrasekar (2014) conducted a study is to find out whether there are any significant mean differences among personal characteristics such as readers' type, gender, user category, age group and the year of study towards attitude of using electronic information resources in Medical Library, University of Jaffna, Sri Lanka during the year 2013. The study used the questionnaire as a research instrument and a total of 258 usable responses were obtained using random sampling technique. Further, the study employs independent samples t-test and One-way ANOVA (f-test) for the purpose of data analysis. The results revealed that readers' type such as academic staff and students, the year of study of the students and user category (Lecturer, Senior Lecturer, Professor and students) have shown significant mean difference towards the attitude of usage of electronic information resources ($P < 0.05$). But, gender both male and female readers and age group have roughly same level of opinion, which is insignificant.

OBJECTIVES

- To find out the awareness of students about online information resources
- To educate the about various methods of searching online resources
- To analyze and compare student's awareness level before and after the training session
- To understand the effect of training session on students' knowledge about resources

METHODOLOGY

For conducting this research mixed method approach was adopted using survey as tool for data collection before and after the training session. Two questionnaires were developed for the study, one to collect data before the training session and one after the training session to analyses and compare

the awareness level before and after the training session. Sample selected for the study was 100 student teachers studying in the teacher education college. Out of 100 participants 84 participants were present for the study.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1) Overall Awareness Level about Online Information Resource

The graphs shows that 94% student teachers were unaware about the online information resources before the training session whereas after the training session 76% became aware about it. The awareness level increased to 70% after the training session.

2) Awareness about NLIST

The graph shows that 74% student teachers were unaware about the NLIST before the training session whereas after the training session 98 % became aware about it. The awareness level increased to 62 % after the training session.

3) Awareness about Shodhgangotri

The graphs shows that 75% student teachers were unaware about the Shodhgangotri before the training session whereas after the training session 86 % became aware about it. The awareness level increased to 62 % after the training session

4) Awareness about Shodhganga

The graphs shows that 78% student teachers were unaware about the Shodhganga before the training session whereas after the training session 85 % became aware about it. The awareness level increased to 63 % after the training session

5) Awareness about ERIC

The above graphs shows that 94% student teachers were unaware about the ERIC before the training session whereas after the training session 89% became aware about it. The awareness level increased to 83 % after the training session

6) Awareness about DOAJ

The above graphs shows that 94% student teachers were unaware about the DOAJ before the training session whereas after the training session 78% became aware about it. The awareness level increased to 72 % after the training session.

7) Awareness about DOAB

The graph shows that 96% student teachers were unaware about the DOAJ before the training session whereas after the training session 72% became aware about it. The awareness level increased to 68 % after the training session.

8) Awareness about E-Balbharati

The graphs shows that 58% student teachers were unaware about the E-Balbharati before the training session whereas after the training session 100% became aware about it. The awareness level increased to 52 % after the training session.

9) Awareness about E-Pathshala

The graphs shows that 92% student teachers were unaware about the E-Pathshala before the training session whereas after the training session 85% became aware about it. The awareness level increased to 77% after the training session.

Conclusion

Result and finding shows that awareness level of the student teachers was much improved after the training session conducted for the student teachers. Their overall as well as individual awareness level about E-Balbharati, E-Pathshala, Shodhganga, Shodhgangotri, ERIC, NLIST, NDLI, DOAJ and DOAB was improved much as compared to the awareness level before the training session. It shows that this kind of training sessions should be conducted for increasing the awareness about online information resources.

Reference

- 1) <http://cart.ebalbharati.in/BalBooks/ebook.aspx>
- 2) <https://epathshala.nic.in/>, <https://ncert.nic.in/>
- 3) <https://eric.ed.gov/>
- 4) <http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/>
- 5) <http://shodhgangotri.inflibnet.ac.in/>
- 6) <http://nlist.inflibnet.ac.in>
- 7) <https://ndl.iitkgp.ac.in/>
- 8) <https://doaj.org/>
- 9) <https://www.doabooks.org/>

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